

1 LinkC: A software for the measurement and variance component estimation of linkage
2 disequilibria in subdivided populations

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16 **Abstract**

17 LinkC is a reimplementation of the software softwares LinkDis and LinkDos, and allows
18 for estimation of a number of population genetic summaries useful for understanding the
19 presence of linkage disequilibrium, and its biological basis, including a hierarchical
20 portioning of LD for subdivided populations, on large-scale, recently derived molecular
21 population genetic datasets. LinkC is available as a binary for all modern operating
22 systems, as well in the form of source code, <https://github.com/peterdfields/linkc>. LinkC
23 can also be accessed with any internet capable computer through Genepop on the Web:
24 <http://genepop.curtin.edu.au/linkC.html>.

25 Linkage disequilibrium (LD), or the non-random association of alleles at two or
26 more loci, is a central concept in population genetics (Slatkin 2008). LD will be
27 generated by both selective and neutral processes (Ohta 1982) above and beyond
28 structural linkage, including natural selection on non-additive multi-locus interactions
29 (epistasis), genetic drift, population subdivision and bottlenecks, and non-random
30 mating/inbreeding (Slatkin 2008).

31 While there exist a number of software packages for measuring different forms of
32 LD, perhaps the most frequently used package for analysis of a small number of
33 molecular markers for ecological genetic study remains Garnier-Gere and Dillmann's
34 (1992) LinkDos (originally a revision of the program LinkDis provided by Black and
35 Krafur (1985)). Here we describe a full revision of the LinkDos, LinkC, which provides
36 the full functionality of the aforementioned software packages on datasets more
37 consummate with ongoing population genetic research. Specifically, in recent years,
38 population genetic studies have benefitted from using an increasing number of
39 individuals and loci (Lascoux & Petit 2010). Using a comprehensive literature search,
40 Guichoux *et al.* (2011) identified approximately 8000 published population genetic
41 analyses utilizing simple sequence repeats (SSRs) and single nucleotide polymorphism
42 (SNPs) in 2009 alone. Continued advances in second-generation sequencing
43 technologies and precipitous decreases in costs, combined with advances in analytical
44 techniques focused upon these specific datasets, promise to accelerate these trends (Wang
45 & Hey 2010; Cao *et al.* 2011). LinkC is not limited by any particular, pre-defined
46 allocation of populations and/or loci, rather it is only limited by computer hardware limits.

47 The utility of the program, both in its original conception and the presented
48 revision, is the computation of population specific allele frequency tables, the estimation
49 of the Cockerham and Weir (1977) measure of linkage disequilibrium (with a
50 significance test based upon the χ^2 statistic), and, most significantly, a variance
51 partitioning of linkage disequilibrium as described by Ohta (1982). This later summary
52 has been shown to be particularly important in reference to the further understanding of
53 epistatic interactions their role in local adaptation (Ma *et al.* 2010; Huang *et al.* 2012;
54 Csilléry *et al.* 2014).

55 Inputs for LinkC inputs can be generated with any form of text editor or
56 spreadsheet program, or through the use of a utility available in the GENEPOP package
57 (Rousset 2008). LinkC can also be accessed on any computer with an Internet connection
58 through the a publically available webserver, <http://genepop.curtin.edu.au/>, replacing the
59 current “LinkDos on the Web”. Results are available as tab-delimited files suitable for
60 downstream processing.

61 LinkC is written entirely in the C programming language, and so is capable of
62 functioning on any modern OS (flavors of Linux, Mac OSX, and Windows). Multi-
63 platform binaries and source code is available via request from the corresponding author,
64 or through github at <https://github.com/peterdfields/linkc>.

65 **LITERATURE CITED**

- 66 Black WC, Krafur ES (1985) A FORTRAN program for the calculation and analysis
67 of two-locus linkage disequilibrium coefficients. *TAG Theoretical and Applied*
68 *Genetics* **70**, 491-496.
- 69 Cao J, Schneeberger K, Ossowski S, *et al.* (2011) Whole-genome sequencing of
70 multiple *Arabidopsis thaliana* populations. *Nature Genetics* **43**, 956-U960.
- 71 Cockerham CC, Weir BS (1977) Digenic descent measures for finite populations.
72 *Genetical Research* **30**, 121-147.
- 73 Csilléry K, Lagüe H, Vendramin GG, *et al.* (2014) Detecting short spatial scale local
74 adaptation and epistatic selection in climate-related candidate genes in
75 European beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) populations. *Molecular Ecology* **23**, 4696-
76 4708.
- 77 Garnier-Gere P, Dillmann C (1992) A computer program for testing pairwise linkage
78 disequilibria in subdivided populations. In: *J Hered*, p. 239.
- 79 Guichoux E, Lagache L, Wagner S, *et al.* (2011) Current trends in microsatellite
80 genotyping. *Molecular Ecology Resources* **11**, 591-611.
- 81 Huang W, Richards S, Carbone MA, *et al.* (2012) Epistasis dominates the genetic
82 architecture of *Drosophila* quantitative traits. *Proceedings of the National*
83 *Academy of Sciences*.
- 84 Lascoux M, Petit RJ (2010) The 'New Wave' in plant demographic inference: more
85 loci and more individuals. *Molecular Ecology* **19**, 1075-1078.

86 Ma X-F, Hall D, St Onge KR, Jansson S, Ingvarsson PK (2010) Genetic Differentiation,
87 Clinal Variation and Phenotypic Associations With Growth Cessation Across
88 the Populus tremula Photoperiodic Pathway. *Genetics* **186**, 1033-1044.

89 Ohta T (1982) Linkage disequilibrium due to random genetic drift in finite
90 subdivided populations. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of*
91 *the United States of America-Biological Sciences* **79**, 1940-1944.

92 Rousset F (2008) GENEPOP ' 007: a complete re-implementation of the GENEPOP
93 software for Windows and Linux. *Molecular Ecology Resources* **8**, 103-106.

94 Slatkin M (2008) Linkage disequilibrium - understanding the evolutionary past and
95 mapping the medical future. *Nature Reviews Genetics* **9**, 477-485.

96 Wang Y, Hey J (2010) Estimating divergence parameters with small samples from a
97 large number of loci. *Genetics* **184**, 363-U390.

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